
Research

The Contributions of Ghana's Minerals Resources to the Global Economy: Using Bauxite as a Case Study

Anamor Samuel Kofi^{1,6*}, Ahiahonu Desmond Senanu Loveridge², Agyemang Obed³, Nkansah Benjamin Oduro⁴, Agyemang David⁵ Targbwe Rapheka Yah⁶

¹Key Laboratory of Deep Coal Resource Mining, Ministry of Education of China, School of Mines, China University of Mining and Technology, Xuzhou, 221116, China

²Department of Architecture and Urban Planning, Chongqing University China

³Faculty of Mining and Mineral Technology, University of Mining and Technology, P.O. Box 273, Tarkwa, Ghana

⁴School of Safety Engineering, China University of Mining and Technology, Xuzhou, 221116, China

⁵Mine Production and Continuous Improvement, Perseus Mining Ghana Limited, Ayanfuri, Central Region, Ghana

⁶State Key Laboratory of Coal Processing and Safe Mining, China University of Mining and Technology, Xuzhou, 221116, China

Abstract: Empirical research shows that most African countries (for example, Ghana) are rich in natural resources and contribute their resources to the economic growth and development of the global economy. Ghana has valuable, semi-valuable, and industrial mineral resources—ideal geological and metallogenic conditions, policy orientation, and social and macroeconomic stability. Furthermore, the correlation analysis method combines information gathered from literary works with the co-authors' questions, the Supreme Court, administrative records, printed and digital sources discoveries on the factors and conditions of the mining process in the country. Which characterizes the intensity of mining production—calculating the correlation between each annual output based on the mining variables using several countries and mining communities' factors that were determined and utilized as the comparison sequence. Ghana's impact on the global bauxite mining industry cannot be overstated, given that the West African nation possesses some of the world's largest reserves of this restorative material. Ghana has significantly impacted the extraction, refining, and utilization of bauxite globally. According to the study's findings, Ghana's mining operations for bauxite and other minerals are predominantly concentrated in the Ashanti, Western, Northern, Eastern, and Central regions, with the Brong-Ahafo region used as the study's focus on the global economy. The research also investigates Ghana's ability to attract investors to utilize these abundant resources for world production and the potential implications of bauxite mining on a global scale. Adopting measures and technical solutions have been presented to decrease the effects of illegal mining on the Environment's damage and health risks in the mining zones.

Keywords: Ghana, Bauxite mining, Political, Mineral resources, Economy, Law, Investment

*Corresponding Author: Anamor Samuel Kofi (kofianamor3@outlook.com)

Accepted: 09 April, 2023; **Published:** 18 April, 2023

How to cite this article: Anamor Samuel Kofi, Ahiahonu Desmond Senanu Loveridge, Agyemang Obed, Nkansah Benjamin Oduro, Agyemang David, Targbwe Ropheka Yah (2023). *The Contributions of Ghana’s Minerals Resources to the Global Economy: Using Bauxite as a Case Study*. *North American Academic Research*, 6(4), 71-86. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7838776>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher’s Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2023 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

Ghana, located in West Africa, is renowned for its abundant natural resources, including bauxite, as depicted in Figure 1-1 to Figure 1-4 by country and others in the global mining arena in Ghana (2009 – 2021). Since the 15th Century, when Ghana was referred to as the "Gold Coast^[1, 2]," mining has been an important economic activity in Ghana. Ghana is Africa's second-largest gold producer after South Africa^[3], and mining accounts for about 5% of the country's gross domestic product^[4]. Before independence in 1957^[5], private foreign investors, mainly the British, dominated the mining industry. After independence, the government established state-owned firms and bought existing mining concerns, shifting industry ownership. At the time of independence, the government's primary purpose was to maximize state revenue and provide jobs for Ghanaians. Ghana has established itself as a pioneer in responsible and effective bauxite mining. Ghana's importance in the global economy will expand as demand for this resource rises, from advancements in sustainable mining techniques to investments in local communities and infrastructure. As a result, the state took ownership and control of its mineral resources, particularly the mining industry. From 1957 until the early 1980s, the state dominated the mining sector with minimal private engagement^[6, 7]. As previously stated, the state's purpose at independence was to manage the mineral resources, maximize state revenue, and create jobs. State-owned firms were, however, not treated with economic prudence or sustainability. The Minerals Commission oversees the exploration, development, and exploitation of mineral resources in Ghana's mining industry. The Commission guarantees that mining corporations comply with environmental and safety standards and fairly compensate communities impacted by mining activity^[8]. Ghana's mining industry has given the country advantages and difficulties. It has contributed significantly to the country's economic progress by providing jobs, generating funds, and attracting foreign investment. Contrary to popular belief, mining is also responsible for environmental damage, societal strife, and human rights violations. Overall, the mining industry plays a vital role in Ghana's economy. Throughout the process, the government is committed to ensuring that all stakeholders benefit from the process sustainably and responsibly.

Figure 1-1 Global bauxite production ^[9]

Figure 1-2 Global gold production^[9]

Figure 1-3 Global diamond production^[9]

Figure 1-4 Global manganese production^[9]

2. Overview of Ghana

2.1 Geography

Ghana is a country in West Africa with a diversified geography of tropical rainforests, rolling hills, and sandy beaches^[10]. It has a total land area of around 238.53 square kilometres and over 31 million inhabitants. Each of Ghana's ten regions has its different terrain and climate. And is bordered to the west by Cote d'Ivoire, north by Burkina Faso, east by Togo, and south by the Gulf of Guinea. The country lies between 4.5° and 11° N latitude and 3.5° W and 1.2° E longitude. Two major physical zones dominate the landscape; the coastal plains in the south and the forested plateaus in the north. The coastal lowlands have sand beaches, lagoons, and mangrove swamps^[11]: Several rivers flow through the northern forested plateaus, including the Black Volta, White Volta, and Red Volta. Mount Afadja, 885 meters above sea level, is Ghana's highest point^[12, 13]. The country's climate is tropical and humid, with two distinct seasons; the rainy season from April to October and the dry season from November to March. Ghana's location has had a significant impact on its history and culture. During the colonial period, the country's location on the coast made it a centre for trade and business. The landscape diversity has also influenced the growth of many economic sectors, including agriculture, mining, and tourism.

2.1.1 Political History

Ghana's political history dates back to the early 19th Century when European nations vied for regional dominance^[14]. In 1874, Britain seized possession and founded the Gold Coast Colony^[15]. In 1960, the colony achieved its independence and became the Republic of Ghana^[16]. Kwame Nkrumah, Ghana's first president, profoundly impacted the country's political scene. He advocated for Pan-Africanism and African socialism and implemented industrialization measures. In 1992, after a succession of military coups, Ghana adopted a new constitution and returned to democracy^[17]. Since then, multiple democratic elections have been held, with power alternating between the N.D.C. and the N.P.P. A GDP per capita of over \$2,200 in 2020 reflects the nation's substantial economic development over the past few decades. However, Ghana continues to face several difficulties, such as extreme deprivation and corruption. Ghana's attempts to advance democracy and sound governance have recently attracted attention on a global scale. Aiming to diversify its economy and draw in outside capital: the nation has also emerged as a regional leader in producing cocoa, gold, and oil in Africa. Table 2-1 compares national per capita income based on the percentage growth rate and G.D.P. per capita.

Table 2-1 Compares the G.D.P., per capita income, and other economic indicators for different African nations^[18].

Country	Population	Nominal GDP(BillionUS\$)	Per capita(US\$)	Percentage Growth Rate(%)
Ghana	34,121,985	75	2,368	2.90%
Liberia	5,384,515	3.9	735	2.18%
Togo	8,806,874	8	960	2.52%
Burkina Faso	22,465,443	18	824	2.55%
Zambia	19,785,797	27	1,348	2.76%
Nigeria	220,075,973	504	2,326	3.41%
Guinea	14,103,629	19	1,345	2.39%
Zimbabwe	15,452,140	38	2,420	2.11%
Ivory Coast	28,160,015	68	2,418	2.52%
Senegal	17,946,407	27	1,558	2.58%

2.1.2 The Economy of Ghana

The Ghanaian economy has experienced the fastest growth in Africa. Over time, the nation has been able to maintain a macroeconomic environment that is reasonably stable, which has increased the number of foreign investments. Ghana's three main economic sectors are agriculture, mining, and services. Ghana's primary cash crop and source of a sizable portion of its export revenue is cocoa; the other significant resources the nation exploits are gold, diamond, limestone, and manganese.

There have been positive developments in Ghana's economy, but several unresolved issues remain. These include a significant youth unemployment rate, inadequate facilities, and limited financing availability. The National Entrepreneurship and Innovation Plan, which offers grants and assistance to start-ups and small firms, is one of the government's strategies to solve these issues^[19]. As a result, agriculture, mining, and services have driven mainly Ghana's growth. Based on the contributions of minerals resources and the production and mining of bauxite resources in Ghana. The administration has implemented programs encouraging economic expansion, attracting foreign investment, and addressing economic problems^[20]. Ghana is well-positioned to continue its economic growth trajectory with ongoing infrastructure investment and adopting policies to address the financial issues.

2.2 Materials & Methods

Pertinent details concerning mining communities concerning international and national legislations, along with the types of transgressions committed by mining companies against these rights, will be acquired through an extensive exploration of relevant legal instruments, laws, and documents in libraries. Other sources, including the Supreme Court, various administrative records, and printed and digital sources, will be consulted. Shall rely on the experiences of mining communities, including observations and testimonials of particular mining community residents.

3. Mining Laws and Regulations In Ghana

3.1 Mining Investment Laws

The importance of mining investment legislation in Ghana has increased recently as the nation has seen growth in mining activities. Ghana has established various laws and regulations regulating mining activities to control and safeguard investors. The Minerals and Mining Act, 2006 (Act 703) and the Minerals and Mining (Amendment) Act, 2015, are two of these laws of particular importance. (Act 900)^[21]. The Minerals and Mining Act, 2006 (Act 703) governs Ghana's mining industry^[22]. This law covers all aspects of mining, including site rehabilitation and the discovery and exploitation of minerals. Additionally, it creates the Minerals Commission as the regulatory agency in charge of regulating the nation's mining operations.

The introduction of the Minerals and Mining (Amendment) Act in 2015 (Act 900) aimed to address problems that arose while implementing the Minerals and Mining Act of 2006^[23]. This law aims to protect the Environment, encourage local participation in the mining industry, and provide for the confiscation of equipment used in unauthorized mining operations.

In addition to these laws, mining companies operating in Ghana must abide by additional rules and regulations. For instance, mining companies must secure the proper permits and licenses before starting mining operations. Additionally, they must follow environmental laws and use ethical mining techniques.

In essence, Ghana's mining investment laws aim to preserve the investors' capacity to operate in a consistent and foreseeable regulatory framework while safeguarding the country's and its citizens' interests^[24, 25]. These laws and regulations will probably change as long as Ghana's mining sector continues to expand to keep the industry viable and advantageous for all parties involved.

3.2 Mining Act 2006 (Act 703)

Aiming to control and manage the development of Ghana's natural resources, the new Minerals and Mining Act 2006 (Act 703) also addresses issues about acquiring mineral rights, the Environment, public health and safety, land usage,

and community relations. The Act outlines laws for the ownership of minerals, the forced purchase of land for mining purposes, the application for mineral rights, and the reservation of land from mining. It also establishes the Minerals Commission as the primary regulating agency for the mining industry. The Act also includes provisions for safeguarding public health and safety, preventing environmental deterioration, and advancing the welfare of mining communities^[26, 27].

4. Ghana Bauxite Mining Zone

4.1 Bauxite Deposits

Ghana is one of China's major bauxite suppliers and has significant deposits and high mineral grades, as seen in **Figures 4-1 to 4-2**. As indicated in **Table 4-1 to 4-2**, the majority of Ghana's bauxite deposit areas, such as the Western Province's Afo-Sefwi Bekwai (Awaso), the Ashanti Province's Aya Nyinahin, the Eastern Province's Atewa Range (Kibi), and the Eastern Province's M.T. Ejuanema. The Western Province's Afo-Sefwi Bekwai (Awaso) region has granted mining rights to the G.B.C. Bauxite reserves were first uncovered in Ghana's Awaso region in 1921. Ghana's primary bauxite deposits are in Awaso, Kibi, M.T. Ejuamena, and Nyinahin. Ghana's bauxite reserves are estimated to amount to 554 million metric tons, with the Awaso deposit actively producing and exporting predominantly to Europe since 1942. According to Achiaw, Ghana's refinery and bauxite deposits can yield 1.5 to 2 million tons of alumina annually.

Figure 4-1 Map distinct substantial resources deposits region of Ghana

In 1940, the Ghana Bauxite Corporation was established, following the mining authorization granted to the British Aluminium Company in 1928; In 1974, the Ghanaian government acquired 55% of the business, making it the largest stakeholder^[28, 29]. In 1982, Alcan bought Britannia Aluminum. The Ghanaian government sold Alcan its 45 to 80% holding in G.B.C. in 1988^[30], giving it an 80% stake in Ghana's bauxite and elevating Alcan to the company's most significant shareholder position. Rio Tinto acquired Alcan before the end of 2007, and the business was renamed Rio Tinto Alcan. In February 2010, Chongqing Bosai Mining Group Co., Ltd. acquired all of Rio Tinto Alcan's shares, making it a significant shareholder^[31].

Ghana's largest bauxite mine is the Aya Nyinahin one in Western Province. E.C.G. received the mining permit from the previous administration. Following the shift in the governing party, the mine has faced numerous legal disputes and challenges. Residents and environmental organizations have hampered it at the same time. Nationalizing mining rights is a top priority for the present administration. No individual or organization received the remaining two tenements. Tema or Secondi-Takoradi are the destinations for transporting bauxite for processing because of the pre-existing infrastructure in these cities, including docks and rail networks.

Figure 4-2 illustrates Ghana's estimated reserves and average mineral composition of significant mining areas. (a) Afo-Sefwi Bekwai (Awaso) 19 reserves (million tons) (b) Aya Nyinahin 350 reserves (million tons) (c) Atewa Range (Kibi) 180 reserves (million tons) (d) M.T Ejuanema 5 reserves (million tons)

Table 4-1 Larger Mining Areas in Ghana

Destination	Region
Obuasi	Ashanti Region
Iduapriem (Tarkwa)	Western Region
Damang	Western Region
Prestea /Bogoso	Western Region
Wassa	Western Region
Kenyasi	Brong-Ahafo Region
Akyem	Eastern Region
Chirano	Western Region
Teleku Bokazo, Nzema	Western Region
Ayanfuri	Central Region
Amansie West	Ashanti Region

Kwabeng	Eastern Region
Osino	Eastern Region
Awaso	Western North Region
Nsuta	Ashanti Region

Table 4-2 Smaller Mining Areas in Ghana

Destination	Region
Odumpara Bepo	Eastern Region
Nkwanta Bepo	Eastern Region
MT. Kwakwati near Akwadum	Western Region
Range of hills trending Northwards from M.T Kwantama	Western Region
Range of hills between Asempaneye and Pomakrom	Eastern Region
Kwamisasa Bauxite Deposit	Western Region
Range northeast of Awuakrom	Ashanti Region
Kansiri Hill near Edubia	Ashanti Region
Mpuasu Hills	Brong Ahafo Region

5 Current Bauxite Mining Situation

In Ghana, industrial-scale mining for bauxite and other solidified minerals started in the 1970s^[32]. Bauxite mining is currently in an adequate state, nevertheless. Numerous issues have plagued the nation, including social unrest, environmental deterioration, and an ineffective government.

There have been some constructive advances in recent years. The government has taken action to solve some challenges, and community support for sustainable mining techniques is growing. However, much more effort must ensure that Ghana's bauxite mining sector is sustainable and profitable for all parties involved.

5.1 Bauxite-Related Policies and Export Prices in Ghana

Mahamudu Bawumia, the vice president of Ghana, is dedicated to utilizing the nation's vital natural mineral resources, such as bauxite, to accelerate the country's rapid economic development. The government recently established the Ghana Bauxite Committee, presided over by the Ghana Minerals Committee and to enhance bauxite development and export management^[33, 34]; it intends to present legislation in Congress to establish the Ghana Bauxite Aluminium Comprehensive Development Authority. The government also plans to switch from exporting unprocessed bauxite ore to a whole industry chain with deep processing and preliminary refinement. The government of Ghana plans to employ a consulting company to investigate the nation's bauxite reserves thoroughly. The Ghanaian government won't issue bauxite mining permits until the exploration is complete. In contrast, the Ghanaian government encourages people and companies to submit declarations of intent for cooperation and detailed cooperation plans on bauxite resources in advance. Currently, the government wishes to collaborate in two key directions. The first is that investors will invest in the mining and refining of bauxite. The distribution of the revenues will be 55% (negotiable)^[35]; In exchange for mining rights, the government must construct the necessary infrastructure. The current export price of bauxite is \$400 per ton^[36], the cost of initial processing is between \$800 and \$1,200 per ton^[37], and the cost of final processing is \$1,900 per ton^[38].

5.1.1 Bauxite Mining in Ghana and its Effects on the Environment

It frequently calls for strip mining of topsoil, which calls for removing any remaining forest cover. Additionally, the rate of deforestation in West African nations increased by 60% in 2018 compared to 2017^[39]. Global Forest Watch figures

show that much destruction occurred inside protected areas. Deforestation has terrible effects. In Ghana, the agricultural sector accounts for around a third of all jobs. These farmers have endured drought and temperatures as high as 43 degrees Celsius (109 degrees Fahrenheit)^[40], which scientists have linked to climate change brought on by deforestation because tropical forests release water and control air temperature. According to Ghana's Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology, and Innovation, rainfall has decreased by 20% over the past few decades due to climate change.

5.2 Negotiations between the Ghana government and enterprises

During the vice president of Ghana's visit to China in June 2017, an agreement of cooperation with China Railway was signed—around \$2 billion worth of projects in total. In May 2017, the Ningxia Tianyuan Manganese Industry Group and the Vice President of Ghana signed a memorandum of cooperation on the development of bauxite^[41].

6. Additional Significant Minerals in Ghana

Figure 6-1 depicts that Ghana's mineral resources include gold ore, diamond, manganese ore, iron ore, limestone, and bauxite. In the 1980s, Ghana began to privatize and divest itself of its assets, including by welcoming foreign investment into its mining industry, which had previously been state-owned^[42, 43]. American Newmont Goldcorp, Chinese, Canadian, South African, and Australian mining enterprises are among the largest in Ghana.

In its attempts to foster economic growth and development, the government of Ghana has designated the mining industry as a priority area of attention. The Ministry of Lands and Natural Resources is working to grow the sector by establishing a Mining Development Fund, among other initiatives. This fund will finance exploration, mining operations, and infrastructure development. Ghana has made considerable strides in strengthening its mining industry in recent years. Existing mines expanded, and several new mines developed. The country is currently home to some of the largest gold mines in Africa, including the AngloGold Ashanti-operated Obuasi mine.

Figure 6-1 Six different types of mineral resources. (a) Gold ore (b) Diamond (c) Bauxite (d) Manganese ore (e) limestone (f) Iron ore (Source: Modified from different online website)

6.1 Challenges

Illegal mining, which makes up much to 30% of the nation's total gold production, is one of the biggest problems^[44]. Illegal miners frequently work without adhering to appropriate safety and environmental standards, which can result

in environmental degradation and health risks. A further factor impeding the sector's development is a lack of investment. This restricts access to high-quality ore deposits and prevents the expansion of existing mines, as evidenced by the limited reserves at the Nauli 377 (million tons), Buipe 20.5 (million tons), Bongo Da 15 (million tons), and Oterkpalu 13.2 (million tons) mines, as depicted in **Figure 6-2**. As illustrated in **Figure 6-3**, the reserves at Himakrom total 5.46 million tons, Aketechi 0.81 million tons, Odumasi 1.705 million tons, Kapili Hill 17.31 million tones, Kalimbi Hill 14.33 million tons, and Nsuta 1.45 million tons. Oppon Mansi 150 reserves, as depicted in **Figure 6-4** (million tons). **Figures 6-5 to Figure 6-6** illustrate the Sheini 27 reserves (million tons) and the Pudo 4.5 reserves, respectively.

Figure 6-2 Limestone mining area situations

Figure 6-3 Manganese mining area situations

Figure 6-4 Iron ore mining area situations

Figure 6-5 Iron ore mining area situations

6-6 Iron ore mining area situations

6.2 Results & Discussion

Despite these challenges, there remains tremendous potential in Ghana's mineral production industry. The nation has enough bauxite for aluminium production. The government of Ghana ought to eliminate all security forces from mining concessions^[45], examine any mining-related incidents involving state security forces, and punish those responsible. If Ghana's mineral-based sector addresses the concerns of illicit mining and attracts more investment, it can significantly contribute to economic growth and development. In addition, a fund to established to support the construction of mining settlements, and legislation to enacted requiring mining enterprises to provide social amenities such as schools and health facilities.

7 Conclusion

In conclusion, it is abundantly evident that Ghana's existing mining state for bauxite and other solid minerals possesses significant potential. This sector can potentially boost Ghana's economy if planned and invested properly by government institutions such as NDPC, APNAC Fundo Minerals, I.A.A., and others. These initiatives must incorporate more effective means of financing exploration efforts and improving infrastructure to use these resources effectively. In addition, environmental restrictions must consider while formulating strategies for upcoming developments; there is no denying that Ghana gains a great deal from the amount of mineral wealth it possesses.

Abbreviation

Abbreviation	Actual Meaning
N.D.C.	National Democratic Congress
NPP	New Patriotic Party
G.D.P.	Gross Domestic Product
G.B.C.	Ghana Bauxite Company Ltd
E.C.G.	Exton Cubic Group
NDPC	National Development Planning Commission
APNAC	African Parliamentarians Network Against Corruption
I.A.A.	Internal Audit Agency

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: We thank the ultimate God who created the universe for our entire being and the ability to structure this research article.

Expansioniate the following individuals a responsibility of appreciation for their invaluable assistance: Shayanowako Michael Kundai, PhD candidate of Mining engineering at China University of Mining and Technology, Xuzhou, China, Amartey Ernest Nii Laryea, PhD candidate of safety engineering and mining engineering, respectively, at the China University of Mines and Technology in Xuzhou, China.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Peters WDJTotaDGuGi. Gold Trade and Gold Mining in the 15th to 18th Century at the Gold Coast (Ghana) and the Activities of the Brandenburg-Prussians[J].1986, 15.
- [2] Hymer S. The political economy of the Gold Coast and Ghana[J].1969.
- [3] Kofi Bempah CJThate. Mining related arsenic problems in Ghana[J].2015, 5(2).77-82.
- [4] Kuranchie-Mensah EB, Amponsah-Tawiah KJJoIE, Management. Employee motivation and work performance: A comparative study of mining companies in Ghana[J].2016, 9(2).255-309.
- [5] Huq MM. **The economy of Ghana**. Springer. 1989.
- [6] Akabzaa T, Darimani AJTWN. Impact of mining sector investment in Ghana: A study of the Tarkwa mining region[J].2001, 11(2).47-61.
- [7] Adu-Ampong EAJTP, Development. Historical trajectories of tourism development policies and planning in Ghana, 1957–2017[J].2019, 16(2).124-141.
- [8] Wan PMJJTEL, Society. Environmental justices and injustices of large-scale gold mining in Ghana: A study of three communities near Obuasi[J].2014, 1(1).38-47.
- [9] **Mining Industry Statistics and Data** [<https://ghanachamberofmines.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/Facts-and-Figures-2021.pdf>]
- [10] Larsen TBJRtI, Game Do, Wildlife G. The butterflies of Ghana-their implications for conservation and sustainable use[J].1994.
- [11] Allersma E, Tilmans WMJO, Management C. Coastal conditions in West Africa—A review[J].1993, 19(3).199-240.
- [12] Wadei B, Appiah DO. A Systematic Discourse of Mining as a Land Use Activity on Water Resources in Ghana[J].
- [13] Yakubu CI, Ferreira VG, Asante CYJG. Towards the selection of an optimal global geopotential model for the computation of the long-wavelength contribution: A case study of Ghana[J].2017, 7(4).113.
- [14] Greene SE. **Sacred sites and the colonial encounter: A history of meaning and memory in Ghana**. Indiana University Press. 2002.
- [15] Shumway R, Belmessous SJEbTNEE, -. Palavers and treaty making in the British acquisition of the Gold Coast colony (West Africa)[J].2014.161-185.
- [16] Fuseini I, Kemp JJJLup. A review of spatial planning in Ghana's socio-economic development trajectory: A sustainable development perspective[J].2015, 47.309-320.
- [17] Owusu MJTJoMAS. Democracy and Africa—a view from the village[J].1992, 30(3).369-396.
- [18] **Population Growth Rate 1950-2023** [<http://www.macrotrends.net/>]
- [19] Atkinson RD, Ezell SJTGII. Principles for National Innovation Success[J].2015.89.
- [20] Owusu-Antwi G, Antwi J, Poku PKJIB, *et al.* Foreign direct investment: a journey to economic growth in Ghana-empirical evidence[J].2013, 12(5).573-584.
- [21] Arthur-Holmes F, Busia KA, Vazquez-Brust DA, *et al.* Graduate unemployment, artisanal and small-scale mining, and rural transformation in Ghana: What does the 'educated'youth involvement offer?[J].2022, 95.125-139.
- [22] MORO A. ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT IN PRACTICE[J].
- [23] Tuokuu FXD, Gruber JS, Idemudia U, *et al.* Challenges and opportunities of environmental policy implementation: Empirical evidence from Ghana's gold mining sector[J].2018, 59.435-445.
- [24] Boakye D, Dessus S, Foday Y, *et al.* Investing mineral wealth in development assets: Ghana, Liberia and Sierra Leone[J].2012(6089).
- [25] Campbell BK. **Regulating mining in Africa: for whose benefit?**, vol. 26. Nordic Africa Institute. 2004.
- [26] **MINERALS AND MINING ACT, 2006 (ACT 703)** [<http://ir.parliament.gh/bitstream/handle/123456789/1884/MINERALS%20AND%20MINING%20ACT%2c%202006%20%28ACT%20703%29.pdf?sequence=1>]

- [27] **Minerals and Mining Act, 2006** [<https://www.mincom.gov.gh/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Minerals-and-Mining-Act-2006-Act-703.pdf>]
- [28] Kuruk P. **Renegotiating transnational investment agreements in the natural resource industries in aid of national development: A case study of bauxite and hydropower supply arrangements between the government of Ghana and the Volta Aluminum Company Ltd.** Stanford University. 1990.
- [29] Bohman A. **Framing the water and sanitation challenge: A history of urban water supply and sanitation in Ghana 1909-2005.** Department of Economic History, Umeå University. 2010.
- [30] Plunkert PAJMY. Bauxite and Alumina[J].1996, 1.97.
- [31] had supplied Taiwan HJAIT. Hydro ends production at Michigan tubing plant[J].2010.
- [32] Kawamoto K. **Diamonds in war, diamonds for peace: Diamond sector management and kimberlite mining in Sierra Leone.** In *High-value natural resources and post-conflict peacebuilding*. Routledge. 2012. 137-162.
- [33] Addy SNJRP. Ghana: Revival of the mineral sector[J].1998, 24(4).229-239.
- [34] Danso F. **Mineral Resource Governance and Human Development in Ghana.** Routledge. 2020.
- [35] Lawer ET, Lukas MC, Jørgensen SHJRP. The neglected role of local institutions in the 'resource curse'debate. Limestone mining in the Krobo region of Ghana[J].2017, 54.43-52.
- [36] Agbolosoo EK. **Mineral processing in a less developed country: Bauxite processing in Ghana.** The University of Arizona. 1991.
- [37] Opoku L, Gyimah AG, Addai BJES, *et al.* Harnessing waste-to-energy potential in developing countries: a case study of rural Ghana[J].2022, 29(38).58011-58021.
- [38] Fluctuation P. Vulnerability of Artisanal and Small Scale Mining to Commodity[J].
- [39] Odijie MEJJoAS. Sustainability winners and losers in business-biased cocoa sustainability programmes in West Africa[J].2018, 16(2).214-227.
- [40] Derbile EK, Bonye SZ, Yiridomoh GYJEC. Mapping vulnerability of smallholder agriculture in Africa: Vulnerability assessment of food crop farming and climate change adaptation in Ghana[J].2022, 8.100537.
- [41] Neal T, Losos E. **The Environmental Implications of China-Africa Resource-financed Infrastructure Agreements: Lessons Learned from Ghana's Sinohydro Agreement.** In. 2021.
- [42] Asante Y, Gyasi EJODIRS. Determinants of foreign direct investment in Ghana[J].2000.1-127.
- [43] Nellis JR, Shirley MM. **Privatization: the lessons of experience.** World Bank Publications. 1992.
- [44] Banchirigah SMJRp. Challenges with eradicating illegal mining in Ghana: A perspective from the grassroots[J].2008, 33(1).29-38.
- [45] Hilson G, Hilson CJ, Pardie SJER. Improving awareness of mercury pollution in small-scale gold mining communities: challenges and ways forward in rural Ghana[J].2007, 103(2).275-287.

Anamor Samuel Kofi

NABPTEX in Automobile Engineering, Akwatia Technical Institute, Eastern Region, Ghana.

Founder and C.E.O. at Anamor Enterprise, Greater Accra, Ghana.

B.Sc in Mechanical Engineering, China University of Mining and Technology Xuzhou, China.

Currently a M.Sc student of Mining Engineering at China University of Mining and Technology Xuzhou, China.

Ahiahonu Desmond Senanu Loveridge

M.Sc Land Resources Management, China University of Mining and Technology

Currently a PhD student in Urban Planning at the Department of Architecture and Urban Planning, Chongqing University China

Agyemang Obed

Currently an Undergraduate student of Mining Engineering at University of Mines and Technology, Tarkwa, Ghana.

Nkansah Benjamin Oduro

Currently an Undergraduate student of Safety Engineering at China University of Mining and Technology Xuzhou, China.

Agyemang David

B.Sc in Mining Engineering, China University of Mining and Technology Xuzhou, China.

Currently a Graduate Mining engineer at Perseus Mining Ghana limited, Ayanfuri, Central Region, Ghana (Mine production and continuous improvement).

Targbwe Rapheka Yah

Currently an Undergraduate student of Mining Engineering at China University of Mining and Technology Xuzhou, China.

